

Extended Data: Impact of diagnostic accuracy on the estimation of excess mortality from incidence and prevalence - simulation study and application to diabetes in German men

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Terminology and symbols are explained in the main text.

Appendix 1: Derivations of Equations (1) and (2) in the main text

In the following we shortly write $\partial_x = \partial / \partial x$ for the partial derivative with respect to the variable $x \in \{t, a\}$. With the assumption that the numbers $H = H(t, a)$ and $C = C(t, a)$ of healthy and diseased individuals aged a at time t , respectively, are partially differentiable functions, the changes in H and C are given by the system:

$$(\partial_t + \partial_a) H = -[i + m_0] H, \tag{A.1}$$

$$(\partial_t + \partial_a) C = i H - m_1 C. \tag{A.2}$$

The incidence rate i as well as the mortality rates m_0 and m_1 are the transition rates in the illness-death model as shown in Figure 1 of the main text. Equations (A.1) and (A.2) are a linear system of partial differential equations (PDEs).

We use equations (A.1) and (A.2) to obtain a one-dimensional PDE describing the temporal and age-related changes in the prevalence

$$p = p(t, a) = \frac{C(t, a)}{C(t, a) + H(t, a)}.$$

As we are interested in the change rate of the prevalence, we use the standard rules of differentiation

$$\begin{aligned} (\partial_t + \partial_a) p &= \frac{(H + C) (\partial_t + \partial_a) C - C (\partial_t + \partial_a) (H + C)}{(H + C)^2} \\ &= \frac{(H + C) [i H - m_1 C] - C [i H - m_1 C - (i + m_0) H]}{(H + C)^2} \\ &= \frac{i H - m_1 C}{H + C} - \frac{C [-m_1 C - m_0 H]}{(H + C)^2} \\ &= i \frac{H}{H + C} - m_1 \frac{C}{H + C} + m_1 \left(\frac{C}{H + C} \right)^2 + m_0 \frac{H C}{(H + C)^2} \\ &= i (1 - p) - m_1 p + m_1 p^2 + m_0 p (1 - p) \\ &= (1 - p) [i + m_0 p - m_1 p] \\ &= (1 - p) [i - p (m_1 - m_0)] \end{aligned}$$

By using the definition $R = m_1/m_0$ and the equation $m = p m_1 + (1 - p) m_0 = m_0 [1 + p (R - 1)]$, some algebra leads to $p(m_1 - m_0) = m p (R - 1) / [1 + p (R - 1)]$, which implies Equation (1). To obtain Equation (2) in the main text, we solve Equation (1) for R .

Appendix 2: Derivation of Equations (3a) and (3b) of the main text

Let Ω be the size of the overall population. With the notation of Figure A.1 (see below), the observed prevalence $p^{(\text{obs})}$ is given by $p^{(\text{obs})} = \{\text{TP} + \text{FP}\} / \Omega = \{\Omega \times p \times se + \Omega \times (1 - p) \times (1 - sp)\} / \Omega$, which implies Equation (3a) of the main text.

Figure A.1: Decision tree in diagnosing a chronic condition ("diseased"). The prevalence of the condition is p , the probabilities of making a correct positive and negative diagnosis are the sensitivity (se) and the specificity (sp), respectively.

Similarly, the observed incidence $i^{(obs)}$ in a small time period Δ is given by $i^{(obs)} = \{\text{TP incident cases in } \Delta + \text{FP incident cases in } \Delta\} / \{\Delta (1 - p^{(obs)}) \Omega\}$. Using $i = \{\text{TP incident cases in } \Delta\} / \{\Delta (1 - p) \Omega\}$ and approximating $(1 - p^{(obs)}) \Omega \approx (1 - p) \Omega$, yields Equation (3b).

Appendix 3: Relation between specificity and sensitivity (Eq. (4) of the main text)

The overall strategy is using Eq. (1) and replace all estimates possibly distorted by imperfect sensitivity and specificity by the adjusted values from Eqs. (3a) and (3b).

For using Equation (1), we need to estimate $\partial p(t, a) = (\partial_t + \partial_a) p(t, a)$ at $t = 2012$. Prevalence data are available in years $t_0 = 2009$ and $t_1 = 2015$. Setting $h := t_1 - t_0$ and approximating $\partial p(t, a)$ by the finite difference $dp(a) \approx \partial p(t, a)$, we obtain

$$dp(a) = [p(t_1, a+h/2) - p(t_0, a-h/2)]/h = [p_1^{(obs)} - p_0^{(obs)}]/[h \{se(a) + sp(a) - 1\}]. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

For the last equation, we defined $p_1^{(\text{obs})} := p^{(\text{obs})}(t_1, a+h/2)$, $p_0^{(\text{obs})} := p^{(\text{obs})}(t_0, a-h/2)$ and used Eq. (3a) together with the assumption that $se_p(t_0, a-h/2) = se_p(t_1, a+h/2) =: se(a)$ and $sp_p(t_0, a-h/2) = sp_p(t_1, a+h/2) =: sp(a)$. The assumption can be achieved by proper choice of the age groups. Apart from $\partial p(t, a)$ we need $p(t, a)$ at $t = 2012$, which we again obtain from $p_0^{(\text{obs})}$ and $p_1^{(\text{obs})}$:

$$p(t, a) \approx [p(t_1, a+h/2) + p(t_0, a-h/2)]/2 = [p_0^{(\text{obs})} + p_1^{(\text{obs})} + 2 sp(a) - 2] / [2 x], \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where, for brevity, we defined $x := se(a) + sp(a) - 1$.

Since the general mortality $m(t, a)$ is assumed to be known from the Federal Statistical Office, the only missing piece for applying Eq. (1) is $i(t, a)$ at $t = 2012$. By applying Eq. (3b) and defining $i^{(\text{obs})} := i^{(\text{obs})}(a)$, $se := se(a)$ we find

$$i(t, a) = [i^{(\text{obs})} + x - se]/x. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

With the new terminology and the abbreviations $\pi := p_0^{(\text{obs})} + p_1^{(\text{obs})}$, $R := R(a)$ Eq. (1) reads as

$$\begin{aligned} dp(a) &= \{1 - [\pi + 2 sp(a) - 2] / [2 x]\} \times \\ &\quad \{[i^{(\text{obs})} + x - se]/x - m (\pi + 2x - 2se)(R - 1) / [2x + (\pi + 2x - 2 se)(R - 1)]\} \end{aligned}$$

or equivalently after multiplying with x and using (A.3)

$$\begin{aligned} x [p_1^{(\text{obs})} - p_0^{(\text{obs})}] / h &= (se - \pi/2) \times \\ &\quad \{i^{(\text{obs})} + x - se - m (\pi + 2x - 2se)(R - 1) / [2se - \pi + R(\pi + 2x - 2 se)]\}. \end{aligned}$$

From this equation, it follows

$$2 R x^2 + x \beta = \gamma \{(\alpha + x) (\beta + 2xR) - 2m(R-1)x^2 - x\delta\}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

with abbreviations $\alpha := i^{(\text{obs})} - se$, $\beta := \pi (R - 1) - 2 se (R - 1)$, $\gamma := h (se - \pi/2) / [p_1^{(\text{obs})} - p_0^{(\text{obs})}]$ and $\delta := m (\pi - 2se)(R - 1)$.

Eq. (A.6) can be transformed into an equivalent quadratic equation

$$x^2 [2R - \gamma \{2R - 2m(R-1)\}] + x [\beta (1 - \gamma) - 2\alpha\gamma R + \gamma\delta] - \alpha\beta\gamma = 0.$$

With $A := 2R - \gamma \{2R - 2m(R-1)\}$, $B := \beta (1 - \gamma) - 2\alpha\gamma R + \gamma\delta$ and $C := -\alpha\beta\gamma$, the required functional form in Eq. (4) $FPR(a) = 1 - sp(a) = 1 - \Phi(se, p, i, m, R) = se - x$ can be obtained by solving the quadratic equation: $Ax^2 + Bx + C = 0$.

This leads us to following algorithm, which is the basis for [Bri20b]:

1. Draw a random sample of se from the range of possible values.
2. Calculate A, B, C and determine the zeros of the quadratic equation $Ax^2 + Bx + C$.
3. Let $x_{1/2}$ be the (not necessarily different) zeros, calculate the associated $FPR_{1/2}$ and $sp_{1/2}$.
4. Calculate p and i from Eq. (3a) and (3b) for each $sp_{1/2}$ and reject the sp which implies any of the following epidemiological implausible conditions: $sp < 0$, $sp > 1$, $p < 0$, $i < 0$, $p > 1$.

References

[Bri20b] Brinks R, Tönnies T, Hoyer A. Estimation of excess mortality from incidence and prevalence: impact of diagnostic accuracy (Version 01), 2020. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4302183>